

DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS THROUGH THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI

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Abstract: In the article, opinions are expressed about the impossibility of fully analyzing Navoi's works and giving a proper critical assessment of his characters in the class, therefore special attention should be paid to the experience of independent reading of Alisher Navoi's works and independent work on them.

Key words: Layli and Majnun, Hayrat-ul-abror, Muhokamat-ul-lugatain, interactive games, "Farhad and Shirin", world and man, individual and society, the essence of life and the meaning of human life, life and death, wisdom and ignorance, truth and lies, good and evil, friendship and enmity, love and loyalty, religion and betrayal, virtue and sin, halal and haraam, generosity and stinginess, sincerity and hypocrisy.

Immortal works created by Navoi remained forever as an inexhaustible spiritual property. With this rich heritage, the Uzbek nation has rightfully taken its place among the nations that have created great literature in the world. In the Turkic world, there has never been such a great writer before or after him.

"Considering the place of the national and universal ideas deeply expressed in the works of Alisher Navoi in the world civilization and increasing the intellectual potential of the growing young generation, considering their incomparable importance in raising high moral qualities in their hearts, as well as the literary and literary works of the great poet and thinker. It is important to further research and widely promote the scientific heritage in our country and internationally" said our President. This is one of the urgent tasks in today's education.

Alisher Navoi said how difficult it is to develop the Turkish literary language, make it popular, and recognize this language in the world of poetry. he

understood well that it is necessary to create an equal literature and he was able to fulfill such a great task. It should be said that Navoi thinks about the relationship between the Turkish and Persian languages in a number of his works. For example, in the "Hayrat-ul-Abror" epic, the Persian poet is happy to read works written in their native language, and Turks deserve to enjoy such wealth, at the end of "Layli and Majnun" he narrated this narration in Turkish. He writes that among the Turks there are many people with good and pure perception. "Muhokamat-ul-lughatayn" compares the power of expression of Turkish and Persian. Based on such evidence, the linguistic problem that interested Alisher Navoi all his life and forced him to think was the relationship between the Turkish and Persian languages, and his desire to prove that the expressive power of the Turkish language is not less than the impressiveness of the Persian language.

Based on the above, interactive methods are also important in teaching Navoi's heritage to today's students. Such methods are highly effective in motivating students. Platforms for creating interactive games: Quizlet, LearningApps, Playfactile, Classtools.net. On these platforms, it is possible to create colorful and meaningful didactic games using various forms of tests, puzzles, flashcards, QR-games, questionnaires, diagrams, cognitive maps, cards. In the process of using such interactive games, students work individually or in groups to answer questions. In its place, it helps to develop their skills of working together, critical thinking, and finding solutions to problems, and to strengthen their knowledge of theoretical and practical issues of science.

Through the works of Alisher Navoi, students learn about the essence of life and humanity, individual and society, the essence of life and the meaning of human life, life and death, enlightenment and ignorance, truth and lies, good and evil, friendship and enmity, love and loyalty, piety and betrayal, good and bad, honest and bad, generosity and stinginess, sincerity and hypocrisy, let's talk about all the eternal and eternal topics, values and concepts, virtues and vices that have occupied the mind and heart of mankind, they will find profound and artistically

high thought observations. This process teaches students to critically evaluate the work of characters in a work of art. For example, in the 9th grade, the teacher introduces students to Alisher Navoi's epic "Farhad and Shirin". That is, the second epic in Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa" is called "Farhad and Shirin" and was completed in 1484. Navoi's epic "Farhad and Shirin" consists of 54 chapters and 5782 verses, of which the prologue includes 11 chapters. tells about the events of the epic. Then he asks the students the following questions;

1. What feelings and thoughts occupied Farhad when he saw Shirin in the mirror?
2. How did feelings and experiences manifest in Farhad?
3. How did Shirin evaluate Farhad's feelings?
4. What noble qualities did Alisher Navoi appreciate in the characters of Farhad and Shirin?
5. What negative qualities are reflected in the epic and in which characters is this shown?
6. What qualities did Alisher Navoi glorify and criticize in the epic "Farhad and Shirin"?

Among the complex questions asked in the research process are questions aimed at explaining the main idea of the author. With the help of such questions, students will be able to determine the moral point of view of the author and thereby make a critical assessment of the characters. For example:

- 1) Alisher Navoi asks his students what moral qualities are important?
- 2) What place do Farhad and Shirin occupy in the understanding of moral qualities?

Research is primarily a method of creative activity. In this process, students will identify the unique aspects of the character of the work's character based on research. In this process, the organization of mutual discussions of students gives effective results. In literature classes, students have the opportunity to meet people from various fields of society. Comprehension of works of art with deep content and making a critical judgment about them

requires students to perform complex mental processes. For this, the students had to spend a certain amount of mental and physical effort. The characters of the work had a significant impact on the feelings of the students. Although the students had some difficulty in reading and understanding the works of Alisher Navoi, they began to look at the heroes of the saga with special interest. The students' difficulties in understanding the language of Alisher Navoi's works caused them to slow down their critical thinking. In order for the readers to analyze the epic in every way and give a critical assessment of its characters, it is necessary to first understand the language of the work. Readers need to understand the content of the text in order to critically assess the heroes of the epic. The characters are required to be able to look at their activities as a component of their experience. Readers need to be able to speak the language of the work in order to understand and think about the epic. When making a critical assessment of the heroes of the epic, students should not act on the basis of the principle "I like this character and I don't like that one." When they think about the plot of the epic, they should be able to feel themselves in the bosom of objective reality. Only then can they think about the characters as their peers, neighbors, neighbors, and relatives.

In short, it is impossible to fully analyze Navoi's works and give a proper critical assessment to his characters in the lesson. Therefore, special attention is paid to the experience of independent reading of Alisher Navoi's works and independent work on them. In order to sufficiently analyze the activity of any of the heroes of any artistic work and give it a critical assessment, it is necessary to fully master the text of the work. Because the composition of the work of art represents a system of images. It is important for students to correctly perceive the space and time represented in the work so that they can make a proper critical assessment of the characters of the work of art.

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